

HBP Leaders' Commitment to Equal Opportunities and Inclusiveness

The HBP strives, by all means, for equal opportunities for all affiliated personnel, at all career levels and functions, with a specific focus on gender. In this respect, the HBP intends to be a role model for complex large-scale science projects.

As a person with leadership responsibility affiliated to the HBP, I recognise the importance of Equal Opportunities for the HBP, and support the principles set out in the **HBP Vision to Work for and Engage in Activities and Research for Equality in the HBP** and the **HBP Mission for Equal Opportunities** (below).

Furthermore, I undertake to contribute to achieving the Vision and Mission by following the **HBP checklist for Equal Opportunities** (below) according to my area of responsibility. I will make best possible use of all the HBP's guiding documents on equality and help provided by the HBP's Diversity and Equal Opportunities Committee.

I am thereby following European Directives for H2020-funded projects and am also making an active contribution to the excellence of the HBP.

First Name Last Name / HBP Partner Institution Date,

Attachments:

- HBP Vision to Work for and Engage in Activities and Research for Equality in the HBP
- HBP Mission for Equal Opportunities
- HBP Equal Opportunities Checklist

Please send the signed letter to: Karin.Grasenick@convelop.at

HBP Vision to Work for and Engage in Activities and Research for Equality in the HBP

HBP will demonstrate how equality can be fostered by a network of outstanding researchers.

It will serve as a best practice example for European funded projects characterised by complexity and spatial remoteness of involved partners.

The HBP will thereby focus on diversity, driven by the appreciation that equal opportunities across different cultures, disciplines, tasks, and sexes contribute to excellence, innovation, and collaboration.

The HBP Mission for Equal Opportunities

The HBP strives, by all means, for **equal opportunities** for all affiliated personnel, at all career levels and functions, with a specific focus on gender. In this respect, the HBP intends to be a role model for complex large-scale science projects.

To achieve these goals, the **Science and Infrastructure Board (SIB)** and the **Directorate (DIR)**, in close collaboration with the **Diversity and Equal Opportunities Committee (DEOC)**, set the framework and measures for equal opportunities. These will help the HBP to address the equal opportunities goals in the EC's H2020 strategy.

Leaders in charge of personnel decisions follow the HBP procedures. They define and justify the composition of their HBP-related staff, their goals and equal opportunities measures.

The HBP reference model for equal opportunities is a cascading model:

- Women and men are expected to be represented at each career level in proportion to the level below.
- The initial figures are derived at the level of PhD students and Postdocs, based on ratios from sources like the European SHE FIGURES, and/or organisations considered as best practice for each Work Package or Task.
- If there is a significant difference, the responsible leaders will check closely to try to find the reason. If the reason is discrimination, the HBP will endeavour by all means to fix that.

The HBP fosters a **collaborative culture** that acknowledges and values each individual's contribution to its innovative results, without discrimination.

Leaders of Work Packages, Tasks, or teams are aware that **distributing work and resources** impacts equal opportunities and act accordingly. Each leader and each person affiliated with the HBP contributes to **fairness and equal opportunities** within his or her area of responsibility, following the **checklist for equal opportunities** and the **hiring and (s)election procedures for personnel and representatives** made available to all HBP researchers and staff.

The HBP adopts a learning attitude and will further develop principles, guidelines and procedures. The HBP continuously monitors, improves, and disseminates its achievements, based on internal assessment, as well as on comparison figures taken from institutional documents, international studies and reports.

The related Coordination of Gender Equality Activities Task, in close collaboration with the DEOC (Diversity and Equal Opportunities Committee), supports all leaders and persons affiliated with the HBP in their activities concerning equal opportunities, with a specific focus on gender.

The HBP Equal Opportunities Checklist

The HBP Equal Opportunities Checklist	Yes/No
1) Do we maintain statistics that differentiate gender and career levels of our staff?	
2) Have we checked our statistics against available reference numbers (university data, conference data, SHE Figures, Elsevier-Report, etc.)?	
3) Does the diversity of our team represent the diversity of the available workforce?	
4) Are women and men proportionally represented at all career levels?	
5) Are job advertisements tested with representatives of the target groups to ensure that they are a clear invitation to all genders?	
6) Are the networks and channels for advertising open positions evaluated on a regular basis to ensure that the greatest pool of possible applicants is reached, especially applicants who are underrepresented according to the reference data?	
7) Are all open positions communicated transparently and made easily accessible to the overall pool of applicants with the specific skill profile sought (e.g. scientific background, language competences, etc.)?	
8) Are guidelines and briefings in place for selecting applicants via evaluation of written applications (to counteract unconscious biases in the best possible way, e.g. considering type of contract/framework conditions under which certain achievements have been made)?	
9) Are guidelines and briefings in place for designing and documenting hiring interviews? (to counteract unconscious prejudices in the best possible way)	
10) Are hiring or appointment decisions clearly documented and communicated to all applicants (to give supportive feedback, if possible explaining how the decision was reached, in accordance with national regulations)?	
11) Are measures in place to support new team members and/or leaders in performing their new tasks to the best of their abilities? (e.g. buddy systems, mentoring, welcome packages, training, etc.)	
12) Do we know and have we made best use of related measures at our organisation or university?	
13) Is the distribution of work and resources within a team or unit re-evaluated on a regular basis? (e.g. time for research and publishing, distribution of additional administrative workload, writing proposals, time in the lab, etc.)	
14) Are measures in place to ensure a collaborative, inclusive culture that values each person's contribution? (e.g. team training, workshops enhancing mutual understanding across all disciplines, cultures, and genders, regularly reflection, surveys, support in conflict resolution, etc.)?	
15) Are measures in place to enable life-work-balance, in collaboration with employers and other relevant organisations? (flexible working hours, Kindergarten, dual career service, coaching)?	
16) Have we provided career advice and development plans for all employees?	
17) Are there measures in place to make sure that these plans are not influenced by unconscious biases? (e.g. comparing and reflecting plans, as well as work distribution in a team, to ensure that the distribution is fair and that what is demanded for a specific career goal does not differ significantly from one person to the other)?	
18) Are measures in place to counteract disadvantages and to give talented people the chance to acquire all necessary skills (e.g. based on cultural differences, less experiences with specific tasks)?	
19) Do we monitor and reflect on data on drop-out rates and career aspirations and career achievements?	
20) Are leaders actually held responsible for an inclusive work environment enhancing equal opportunities within their area of responsibility (e.g. via training or by redefining their area of responsibility)?	